

Micellar catalysis of an iron(III)-MOF: enhanced biosensing characteristics†

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Abstract

Recent years have seen an enormous growth of interest in enzyme mimics based on porous materials as a substitute for natural enzymes. This interest has been increased to a considerable extent due to the fact that they have outstanding chemical and structural features. Herein, $Zr_6O_8(H_2O)_8(FeCl-tcpp)_2(PCN-222(Fe))$ was synthesized via a solvothermal approach with Zr_6 clusters as nodes and Fe–TCPP (TCPP $\frac{1}{4}$ tetrakis(4-carboxyphenyl) porphyrin) as a heme-like ligand and was characterized by various techniques such as XRD, TEM, SEM, XPS, UV-vis and IR. Also, since the achievement of high enzyme-like activity of some nanoparticles has attracted widespread interest in recent years, for the first time, we have applied a significant approach by modifying PCN-222(Fe) with sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) micelles (SDS/PCN-222(Fe)). In an attempt to explore the significance of this procedure, initially, peroxidase and catalase-like activity were investigated through a reaction with a chromogenic substrate 2,20-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt (ABTS). Based on the high peroxidatic activity of SDS/PCN-222(Fe), a visual, sensitive and reliable method was established for detection of H_2O_2 with a linear range of 3–200 mM and limit of detection (LOD) of 2 mM. Also, as an implication of these findings, the SDS/ $Zr_6O_8(H_2O)_8(FeCl-tcpp)_2$ (SDS/PCN-222(Fe)) based system could also be used for glucose assay with a LOD of 3 mM indicating potential applications in clinical medicine. In order to prove this hypothesis, the glucose detection in human serum was determined. Finally, on the basis of SDS/PCN-222(Fe) performance, three natural antioxidants, gallic acid (GA), tannic acid (TA), and ascorbic acid (AA) were applied to explore antioxidant capabilities.

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